

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PRABHU****FIRST NAME: KAMLESH****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2021 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to Turabian, when should one select an endnote over a footnote?

- When the footnotes are long and numerous, thus making the document difficult to read.¹**
- For articles that have two or more authors.
- For blog posts and other postings to Internet media.
- When you quote exact words.

2. According to Turabian, which of the below sources can be considered reliable?

- A book that has no notes or bibliographies.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 160.

- A research article on chemotherapies that was published 20 years ago.
 - A recent article in the Lancet about best epidemiological practices with more than 100 citations.²**
 - A book on reversing climate change published on Amazon by a single author with no peer review.
3. Which of the following is not one of Turabian's recommended strategies for revising your draft?
- Checking paragraphs to ensure that they are relevant to the section.
 - Ensuring that readers can easily identify the introduction, conclusion and claim.
 - Adding complex language to ensure that readers consider the author to be sophisticated.³**
 - Checking for blind spots in the primary argument's reasoning.
4. According to Turabian, which of the below is false about notes and bibliographies?
- A note can include page numbers, but a bibliography does not include page numbers.
 - A note will have the author's first name mentioned before the last name, but the reverse is true for a bibliography.

² Turabian, 41-42.

³ Turabian, 105-108.

- A note will have elements separated by a period, while in bibliographies, elements are separated by commas.⁴
- A note is indented like other paragraphs, while bibliographies have hanging indents.
5. According to Sampson, what is recommended when documenting a literature review?
- Make value judgments.
- Ensure all terminology has been clearly defined.**⁵
- Have a strong topic sentence only for the first paragraph.
- State all the arguments without providing examples.
6. According to Sampson, the selection of measures for specific variables should be based on?
- Correspondence and quality.**⁶
- Reliability and validity.
- Credibility and quality.
- Competency and plausibility.
7. According to Sampson, which of the below procedures is not applicable before data collection for a dissertation?

⁴ Turabian, 154-155.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 32.

⁶ Sampson, 37.

- Prepare the informed consent form that is part of the institutional review board application for human subjects.
 - Prepare aggregate summaries of data and provide them to the organization where the research was performed.**⁷
 - Complete all relevant training that may be necessary in delivering treatment.
 - Select all the participants for the dissertation research.
8. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, what is a defining feature of qualitative research?
- It focuses on objective data.
 - The research methodology is highly structured and rigid.
 - It studies people in their natural environment and explains findings from the research participant's perspective.**⁸
 - It starts with a clear hypothesis that the study aims to test.
9. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, what are the four areas of information needed for most qualitative studies?
- Historical, Analytical, Longitudinal, and Comparative.
 - Contextual, Demographic, Perceptual, and Theoretical.**⁹
 - Statistical, Quantitative, Experimental, and Predictive.
 - Logical, Descriptive, Analytical, and Comparative.

⁷ Sampson, 51.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 144-145.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 443.

10. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, which of the following is not true about synthesis and summary?

- Synthesis is an advanced reading technique, while summary is a basic/intermediary reading technique.
- Synthesis combines information to highlight key points, while summary integrates information to conclude.**¹⁰
- Synthesis focuses on deep details, while summary presents a superficial overview.
- Synthesis creates new perspectives that add value to a discussion, while summary describes the information from the sources.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End. Fourth edition.* Los Angeles: SAGE Publication, Inc., 2019.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research. 2nd ed.* Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.* Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 385-386.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.